

ACCESS-NRI
AUSTRALIA'S CLIMATE SIMULATOR

WORK PLAN

2024-2025

ACCESS-NRI is enabled by the Australian Government through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy, NCRIS.

We at ACCESS-NRI acknowledge the Traditional Owners of the land on which our research infrastructure and community operate across Australia and pay our respects to Elders past and present. We recognise the thousands of years of accumulated knowledge and deep connection they have with all the Earth systems we simulate.

ACCESS-NRI Annual Work Plan

FY2024 - 2025

Executive summary

The ACCESS-NRI annual work plan summarises the major projects and activities planned across the organisation for the 2024-25 financial year, our third year of operation. The work plan has been developed by ACCESS-NRI's leadership team and reviewed by the Scientific Advisory Committee (SAC). It is intended to provide transparency into the work ACCESS-NRI is funded to deliver as well as to promote feedback and discussion with the research communities we support. This our second annual work plan and many of the activities from the previous financial year continue in this new work plan. In most cases this is due to the multi-year nature of projects, which will have updated targets for the coming year.

The 2024-25 work plan details our major projects and activities under 4 broad categories:

- Model Development
- Model Releases & Infrastructure
- Software & Data
- Training & Engagement

Activities include a brief description, activity lead(s), team(s) undertaking the work and an estimate of effort. We encourage the ACCESS community to reach out with any feedback they may have or to discuss opportunities for collaboration related to the annual work plan.

Introduction

ACCESS-NRI, Australia's Climate Simulator, is a national research infrastructure that delivers world-class computer simulations for climate, weather and Earth systems, specifically designed for Australia and the Southern Hemisphere. Our computational Earth system modelling framework, ACCESS, is hosted at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) and enabled by the Australian Government through the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). Launched in 2022, we are now in our third year of operation and the following sections outline the major projects and activities for the 2024-2025 financial year.

The 2024-25 work plan is summarised under 4 broad categories:

- Model Development
- Model Releases & Infrastructure
- Software & Data
- Training & Engagement

Activities include a brief description, activity lead(s), team(s) undertaking the work and an estimate of effort. Each category also lists the ACCESS-NRI Strategic Plan (2022-2027) goals supported by the work. These goals include:

1. Creating an ACCESS model framework which is easier for researchers to develop and use
2. Improve the quality and performance of ACCESS model configurations
3. Make ACCESS output and input data transparent, open and accessible
4. Australian science for Australian model infrastructure
5. Be an organisation where people and partnerships thrive
6. Preparing for future challenges
7. Build a connected community across academia, government, science, industry and society

Note that while Goal 5 is not explicitly listed against any of the work plan categories, it is critical in all our work as an organisation and national research infrastructure.

Model Development

ACCESS-NRI's model development activities aim to build and further develop the Australian Community Climate and Earth System Simulator (ACCESS) framework. This includes the individual model components (e.g., atmosphere, ocean, land surface, ice sheets) as well as the model configurations, which couple together the individual components. In partnership with the Australian research community, ACCESS-NRI will develop a range of coupled model configurations to satisfy different model uses. Details of the planned Model Development activities are listed in Table 1.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 2, 3 and 4

Table 1: Model development activities

Activity	Description	Lead and team(s) involved	Effort*
Ancillary suites and tools	Complete the development and release of AMAMI ancillary manipulation package. Release suites for generating ancillaries for ACCESS-AM3 and ACCESS-CM3 (possibly including CABLE ancillaries with new data sources). If required, prepare ACCESS-ESM1.6 ancillaries for CMIP7 fast-track experiments.	Heidi Nettelbeck <i>Atmosphere Modelling, Ocean Modelling, Land Modelling and Release teams</i>	1 FTE
Atmosphere model development	Release beta versions of ACCESS-AM3 and ACCESS-AM3-BGC, including post-processing in suites. Scope the possibility of having an NRI-supported atmospheric chemistry configuration. Help to support the ACCESS community during the UKMO git migration (if on schedule).	Martin Dix, Claire Carouge, Heidi Nettelbeck <i>Atmosphere and Land Modelling teams (CSIRO in-kind)</i>	1 FTE
Earth system and Coupled model development	ACCESS-ESM1.6 development Flagship release of ACCESS-ESM1.5 with both concentration- and emissions-driven configurations. Release of ACCESS-ESM1.6, including updated WOMBAT and cleanup of CABLE-ESM coupling. Enhance the Payu setup to be more flexible (e.g. for paleo community). ACCESS-CM3 development Beta release of ACCESS-CM3. The necessary steps include merging the NUOPC and ACCESS-AM3 development bases, adaptation of the JULES river	Martin Dix <i>Atmosphere, Ocean and Land Modelling teams (CSIRO in-kind)</i>	>2 FTE

	<p>routing for CABLE, iceberg melt fluxes and optimisation of NUOPC coupling.</p> <p>ACCESS-ESM3 development Release an alpha version of ACCESS-ESM3. Exact configuration depends on CABLE4 development.</p>		
Ocean/sea-ice model development	<p>Release beta version of performant ACCESS-OM3 MOM6-CICE6 RYF and IAF global configurations at 0.25 and 1 deg. Port latest WOMBAT science developments into new generic codebase and make available in ACCESS-OM3, ACCESS-OM2 and ESM1.6. Through consultation with the research community and with other modelling centres, continue to improve/develop configurations involving WW3 and their associated coupling with the ocean and sea-ice.</p>	<p>Chris Bull</p> <p><i>Ocean Modelling team (CSIRO in-kind)</i></p>	>2 FTE
Regional model development	<p>Release NRI-supported configurations of the Regional Nesting Suite (RNS), including documentation for a 2-level nested configuration. Create an alpha release of these configurations with CABLE replacing JULES. Help to support the ACCESS community during the UKMO git migration (if on schedule).</p>	<p>Chermelle Engel</p> <p><i>Atmosphere Modelling team (BoM in-kind)</i></p>	1 FTE
Land model development	<p>Release an alpha version of CABLE4 (standalone). Create and release configurations with proper provenance of input data. Rewrite the MPI implementation of CABLE to work with POP and POPLUC. Implement a basic testing CI pipeline for CABLE. Develop the training for benchcab.</p>	<p>Claire Carouge</p> <p><i>Land Modelling team (CSIRO in-kind)</i></p>	>2 FTE
Ice sheet model development	<p>Establish a team to support development of the Ice-sheet and Sea-level System Model (ISSM) as well as the beta release of an ISSM configuration. Begin development of coupled ice-atmosphere (ISSM-ACCESS-AM3) and ice-ocean (ISSM-ACCESS-OM3) models.</p>	<p>Mike Tetley</p> <p><i>Ice Sheet Modelling team (AAD in-kind)</i></p>	2 FTE
Coastal modelling commons	<p>Initiate coastal ocean modelling commons to support ANCOMS community and scope a super-regional MOM6 configuration. Initial work will focus on sharing existing model configurations and tools.</p>	<p>Helen Macdonald</p> <p><i>Coastal Modelling team (UNSW and ANCOMS)</i></p>	1 FTE

*Full time equivalent (FTE) staff needed to scope, undertake, and deliver activity.

Model Releases & Infrastructure

ACCESS-NRI’s model release and infrastructure activities support the model release and monitoring frameworks used across the organisation. The model release framework is tightly integrated with model development activities and bring modern software development approaches to ACCESS to ensure robust, reproducible and trusted model configurations for our community. Our monitoring framework is an important tool in measuring and understanding ACCESS-NRI’s impact and work this year focuses on establishing usage tracking across the models, software and data we support. Additional activities also include the annual management of the merit-based compute and storage resources at NCI as well as support for the transition of selected tools and infrastructure from the ARC Centre of Excellence for Climate Extremes (CLEX), which concludes in December 2024. Details of the planned Model Releases and Infrastructure activities are listed in Table 2.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 2, 3, 4 and 7

Table 2: Model releases and infrastructure activities

Activity	Description	Lead and team(s)	Effort*
Flagship releases	<p>Work to prepare, build and deploy configurations for ACCESS-NRI supported models and configurations. This includes quality assurance, reproducibility testing and improvements to the standardisation of model output data. Scheduled flagship releases for this FY include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ACCESS-ESM1.5 • ACCESS-CM2 • NRI-supported configurations of the RNS • ACCESS-AM3 • ACCESS-ESM1.6 	<p>Aidan Heerdegen</p> <p><i>Model Release, Atmosphere, Ocean and Land Modelling teams</i></p>	>2 FTE
Release and configuration pipeline improvements	<p>Updates to the model release software pipeline to build, test and deploy all ACCESS-NRI supported models. This includes improvements and extensions to the continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) and model component software as well as the addition of end-to-end provenance for software and data.</p>	<p>Aidan Heerdegen</p> <p><i>Model Release team</i></p>	1 FTE

Monitoring and impact tracking	Updates to the monitoring framework for tracking uptake and impact of ACCESS-NRI infrastructure on the national and international research community.	<i>Aidan Heerdegen</i> <i>Model Release team and cross-organisation</i>	1 FTE
ACCESS-NRI merit allocation	Management of the ACCESS-NRI merit allocation for access to NCI compute and storage resources. These resources are provided to support community members to undertake scientific simulations using ACCESS models and share community reference datasets.	<i>Claire Carouge and Clare Richards</i>	< 1 FTE
Transition of CLEX tools and infrastructure	Support for the transition of any identified CLEX tools and infrastructure that align with ACCESS-NRI supported models, data and tools.	Cross-organisation	< 1 FTE

*Full time equivalent (FTE) staff needed to scope, undertake, and deliver activity.

Software & Data

ACCESS-NRI’s software and data activities focus on supporting tools, workflows and data related to the ACCESS models and data outputs. These include tools and workflows to support model evaluation, the ACCESS-NRI Intake Catalog (for in-depth data discovery) as well as the release and management of ACCESS-related datasets. Work also includes the release of ACCESS visualisations (including open-source code), model optimisation and establishing a software transformation program, which aims to prepare ACCESS for future advances and challenges (e.g., exascale computing, AI/ML, GPUs). Details of the planned Software and Data activities are listed in Table 3.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported: 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6

Table 3: Software and data activities

Activity	Description	Lead and team(s)	Effort*
Model evaluation and diagnostics tools	Continued support for a standardised, reproducible framework for evaluation of ACCESS outputs, including a semi-automated pipeline for a CMIP7	Romain Beucher <i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics, Atmosphere,</i>	>2 FTE

	<p>ACCESS submission. Tools and workflows supported include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ILAMB Workflow • ESMValTool Workflow • Model Live Diagnostics • Community cookbooks and recipes 	<p><i>Ocean, Land and Ice Sheet Modelling teams</i></p> <p><i>(BoM, CSIRO in-kind)</i></p>	
ACCESS-NRI Intake Catalog	<p>The release and support of the ACCESS-NRI Intake tool, which enables the cataloguing and discovery of ACCESS data at NCI as well as integration with the NCI Data Collections (and NCI cataloguing tools).</p>	<p>Romain Beucher</p> <p><i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics, Atmosphere, Ocean and Land Modelling teams</i></p>	1 FTE
Data releases and data management	<p>Release and data management of ACCESS model outputs and related datasets for model evaluation (including merit-based datasets nominated by the Community Working Groups). This work also includes data management and governance support across the tools and resources used with data.</p>	<p>Clare Richards</p> <p><i>Cross-organisation</i></p>	1 FTE
Data visualisation	<p>Create high-impact visualisations to help explain the ACCESS models, data outputs and science across the community. Open access to the visualisation code and tools (wherever possible) as well as visualisation training will be outputs of this work.</p>	<p>Owen Kaluza</p> <p><i>Model Evaluation & Diagnostics Team</i> <i>Outreach & Engagement</i> <i>(Business Team)</i></p>	1 FTE
Model optimisation	<p>Create a set of tools to benchmark and profile the ACCESS models. Improve the performance and parallel scalability of the ACCESS models by optimizing the software and the configurations.</p>	<p>Micael Oliveira and Martin Dix</p> <p><i>Software Transformation, Atmosphere, Ocean and Land Modelling teams</i></p>	1-2 FTE
Software transformation	<p>Assess the emerging HPC, cloud, and data landscape and formulate a strategy to position ACCESS-NRI for AI/ML and GPU-readiness. Establish team/capabilities in this area.</p>	<p>Micael Oliveira</p> <p><i>Software Transformation team</i></p>	1 FTE
Improved observational constraint and	<p>Streamline the data pipeline from TERN to modevaluation.org and to land surface models.</p>	<p>Ben Schroeter and Gab Abramowitz (UNSW)</p>	1 FTE

testing facility for ACCESS-NRI land models	Update the evaluation analysis pipeline to make it faster, more stable and user-friendly.	<i>Land Modelling team and UNSW</i>	
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*Full time equivalent (FTE) staff needed to scope, undertake, and deliver activity.

Training & Engagement

ACCESS-NRI’s training and engagement activities centre on connecting with Australia’s research community and the uptake of the ACCESS models, software and data. These include our annual ACCESS Community Workshop, training program and support for our community working groups, which provide scientific leadership on specific ACCESS component, configuration or research area. Our training program will offer a range of in-person and online events, targeting both new and existing ACCESS users and communities. We will also continue to support and enhance the ACCESS-Hive, which underpins activities across the organisation and is home to our user-facing documentation and user forum. Additional focus areas for the year also include communication and outreach activities and our graduate-style internship program. Details of the planned Training and Engagement activities are listed in Table 4.

Strategic Plan 2022-2027 goals supported by these activities: 1, 4, 6 and 7

Table 4: Training and engagement activities

Project	Description	Lead and team(s)	Effort*
ACCESS Community Workshop	Host and support the annual ACCESS community workshop. Scheduled for September 2024 in Canberra. Work will also include planning and preparations for the 2025 workshop that will be held in the following financial year.	Victoria Allen <i>Business Team</i>	>2 FTE
Community Working Groups	Support for the 6 ACCESS Community Working Groups. This includes facilitating the two-way flow of information between each Working Group and ACCESS-NRI developers and enabling access to HPC resources (compute and storage) at NCI.	Chris Bull, Claire Carouge, Heidi Nettelbeck, Micael Oliveira, Mike Tetley and Spencer Wong. <i>ACCESS-NRI Working Group Liaisons</i>	1–2 FTE

Communication and outreach	Communicating the impact and importance of ACCESS-NRI's software infrastructure and expertise for climate science researchers and decision-makers. This work includes ACCESS-NRI's regular newsletters (ACCESSStory), annual Highlights Report, online communication channels, impact stories, visualisations, media releases and outreach activities.	Natalia Bateman <i>Business Team</i>	1 FTE
Community engagement	Engagement activities that support the two-way interactions between ACCESS-NRI and our users, partners, funders and other NCRIS organisations.	Natalia Bateman <i>Business team and Cross-organisation</i>	1 FTE
ACCESS Workshop Training Day	The 2024 Community Workshop will include a major training event. Planning and preparations for any training related events associated with the 2025 workshop will also be undertaken.	Paige Martin <i>User Training team and Cross-organisation</i>	< 1 FTE
ACCESS-Hive Docs and Forum	Continued development and support of the Hive Docs and Forum. This includes documentation for ACCESS models, tools and data as well as training content.	Heidi Nettelbeck and Paige Martin <i>Cross-organisation</i>	1-2 FTE
User support	Continued support for help requests received through the ACCESS-Hive Forum. This includes triaging posts and connecting users with ACCESS-NRI specialists for assistance with supported software and data, or community experts for topics outside of ACCESS-NRI's areas of expertise.	Paige Martin <i>User Training team and cross-organisation</i>	1-2 FTE
ACCESS user training	Training events for new and existing users. Minor events will include support for hackathon-style events and webinar/information sessions, the majority being targeted at supported models, software and data releases.	Paige Martin <i>User Training team and Cross-organisation</i>	1-2 FTE
Graduate-style program for PhD students	Run an internship program to host 2-4 PhD students at ACCESS-NRI.	Paige Martin <i>User Training team and Cross-organisation</i>	1 FTE

*Full time equivalent (FTE) staff needed to scope, undertake, and deliver activity.

Glossary

Please visit our main website for a compilation of common terms and acronyms used within this document and by the ACCESS community: <https://www.access-nri.org.au/community/access-glossary/>

Acknowledgements

The ACCESS-NRI Annual Workplan was inspired and influenced by [Atlas of Living Australia's Annual Workplan](#):

Atlas of Living Australia (2023) Atlas of Living Australia Annual Workplan 2023-24, Atlas of Living Australia, Publication Series No. 7, Canberra, Australia, pp. 19.

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